

Doing Well by Doing Good Innovations: Outcomes of The "LENTERA Sukamoro" Community Development Program

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ABSTRACT: PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit (PTBA Derti) is a State-Owned Enterprise (BUMN) in the coal mining business. As a coal distribution firm, PT Bukit Asam Unit Dermaga Kertapati is required to practice Corporate Social Innovation (CSI) and environmental social responsibility in the area surrounding its activities. The PTBA Derti CSI program is carried out in Sukamoro Village under the name "LENTERA Sukamoro". It focuses on community development that is commensurate with the community's social, economic, and environmental situations. This study aims to investigate, from the viewpoint of program participants, the results of a corporate social innovation (CSI) initiative in community development. Data was gathered through surveys, questionnaires, and in-depth interviews with 15 LENTERA Sukamoro program participants, PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati, and local government heads and officials. The study discovered that the "LENTERA Sukamoro" program from PTBA Derti was able to solve a variety of difficulties in Sukamoro Village, including a large number of housewives who do not have jobs or engage in productive activities, poverty, a lack of skills, and unproductive land issues. The "LENTERA Sukamoro" program enables the community to enhance its skills and capacities, raise income and welfare, and gain access to renewable energy. This study adds to the limited literature on CSI in Indonesia by examining how commercial organizations in the country contribute to community development through CSI. This study's findings should be valuable to community development practitioners, CSI providers, and researchers.

KEYWORDS- Corporate Social Innovation; Community Development; PTBA Derti; LENTERA Sukamoro Program

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, businesses have gotten more involved in solving societal problems (Pol and Ville, 2009). Drucker (1984) defined firms as actors who may transform social issues into economic opportunities. Increased global inequality (Oxfam, 2019), the pursuit of both economic and social development as espoused by the United Nations' adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015, and the impact of the COVID crisis all call into question the assumption that corporate capitalism meets societal needs (Rocha et al., 2021). As a result, private-sector companies face the problem of addressing social challenges and societal needs (Mirvis et al., 2016; Dionisio & de Vargas, 2020). There is rising international recognition of the need for a global model of sustainable development that ensures a balanced interplay between economic growth, social fairness, and environmental conservation (Santos, 2014). Within this framework, corporate social innovation (CSI) has been viewed as a tool that companies/organizations can use to achieve higher levels of global sustainability.

To co-create something new that offers a sustainable solution to social issues, corporations are looking into new sources and creative ways to partner with social innovators, social enterprises, and governments. This approach expands the roles of various actors and opens up new business opportunities, all the while having an impact on public services, employment, and education (Dionisio & de Vargas, 2022; Mirvis & Googins, 2017; Mirvis et al., 2016). Furthermore, corporate social innovations already take into account the necessity for cross-party collaborations. CSI entails developing and implementing a strategic investment that is managed as a corporate project in order to create a socially relevant innovation system (Yin & Jamali, 2016; Dionisio & de Vargas, 2020). These strategic investments entail the deployment of assets and knowledge through deep collaboration across a firm's operations and with external partners to co-create something new that provides a long-term answer to societal problems (De Silva et al., 2020).

Corporate Social Innovation has been actively explored in Indonesia for many years. This was realized through the development of Law Number 40 of 2008 on Limited Liability enterprises, which stressed that enterprises involved in and related to natural resources should carry out corporate social and environmental duties. To comply with the regulations outlined in the

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Minister of Environment and Forestry Regulation (Permen LHK) Number 01 of 2021, enterprises must participate in the Company Performance Rating Assessment Program (Proper). Each company participating in Proper Beyond Compliance must select one Community development program (Comdev) that is recommended as a flagship initiative and meets social innovation requirements.

In the mining industry, an enterprise commonly uses the term "community development" (CD) to refer to direct or indirect activities carried out in geographically close communities to promote the economy, environment, and society in these communities (Kemp, 2009; Wang et al., 2018). The International Council on Mining and Metals (ICMM, 2005) defines community development as the process of strengthening and improving communities, enhancing people's quality of life, and empowering people to participate in decision-making to achieve greater long-term control over their lives. This definition is found in the community development kit jointly issued by ICMM and World Bank.

PT Bukit Asam Tbk (PTBA) is a state-owned enterprise (BUMN) in the coal mining business. In cooperation with PT Kereta Api Indonesia (PT KAI), a train fleet is used to deliver coal products by road once it has been extracted from the Tanjung Enim Mining Unit (UPTE) mining site. All PTBA Derti operating activities, direct or indirect, have an impact on the local community. As a coal distribution firm, PT Bukit Asam Unit Dermaga Kertapati is required to adopt Corporate Social Innovation (CSI) and environmental social responsibility in the communities where it operates. PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit is located in the center of Palembang City, South Sumatra Province. Palembang City is the capital of South Sumatra Province and is part of a highly developed urban area. As a result, PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit must choose a community development location outside of Palembang City, specifically Sukamoro Village, Talang Kelapa District, Banyuasin Regency, South Sumatra Province.

Sukamoro Village is classified as a developing village (based on the IDM rating for Talang Kelapa District in 2019). There are still numerous unresolved social, economic, and environmental issues in the region. It is well known that there are still numerous cases of poverty, unemployment, low earnings, and a lack of work options due to people's limited abilities. This scenario is aggravated by the large number of women who do not have employment or other economic activities to contribute to the household economy. Having seen this tendency, PT Bukit Asam Unit Dermaga Kertapati chose Sukamoro Village as the site for community development. PT Bukit Asam Tbk Dermaga Kertapati Unit uses the CSI program as a way of showing concern for the community surrounding the company's environment. The CSI program focuses on community development that is in line with the social, economic, and environmental aspects of society. The goal is to create a successful and self-sufficient community that evolves in harmony with the environment.

In order to better understand the community development initiative implemented by PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit in Sukamoro Village, this research will be conducted. Aside from that, this study was undertaken to examine the success of the program that was implemented, as well as to determine the degree of the impact and changes it had on the lives of the inhabitants of Sukamoro Village.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Corporate Social Innovation

Corporate social innovation (CSI) is defined as "an initiative that aims to create both shareholder and social value with the potential to alter the structure of innovation systems, improve employee motivation, and change corporate identities and strategies to increase competitive advantage, while at the same time bringing solutions to societal needs" (Dionisio & de Vargas, 2020; Saka-Helmhout et al., 2024). This notion initially surfaced in 1999, proposing to form strategic partnerships between businesses and civil society by supporting long-term improvements, with the expectation that it would significantly stimulate the business's development (Kanter, 1999). These ideas and processes provide novel approaches to addressing social needs (Mirvis et al., 2016), are "proactively initiated, multilevel in nature, and include bottom-up dynamics" (Stephan et al., 2016), and diverge from the concept of CSR (Saka-Helmhout et al., 2021). Traditional definitions of CSR focus on philanthropic actions that address external challenges and improve business reputations (Dembek et al., 2016). According to Mirvis et al. (2016), there are frequently "significant gaps between stakeholder expectations and corporate social performance" as a result of these CSR initiatives, and they are frequently unsustainable due to a lack of a workable business plan (Sinkovic et al., 2014).

Corporate social innovation (CSI) varies from standard CSR initiatives in various ways (Mirvis et al. 2016). First, traditional CSR initiatives are motivated by philanthropy, whereas CSI is a strategic investment that firms manage similarly to other corporate assets. Second, CSR programs require financial and human resources commitments, whereas CSI involves a corporation in societally relevant R&D and applies the entire range of corporate assets to the difficulties at hand. Third, typical CSR programs frequently involve businesses contracting with nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) or community groups to provide social services. CSI entails broader collaboration across a company's activities and with external partners to co-create something new that gives a long-term solution to social issues. Finally, although CSR can generate goodwill and improve business reputation, CSI

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aspires to establish new revenue streams as well as a more socially relevant innovation system and corporate culture, which can provide a competitive edge.

Businesses that adopt CSI must reevaluate their current business models and create entirely new ones, all the while creating components that enable CSI to be institutionalized. These components include partnerships, new processes, strategic intent and purpose, and outcomes that are advantageous to society and business (Herrera, 2015; Mirvis & Googins, 2017). In practical terms, the idea begins with a strong corporate vision that supports motivating values and creates an environment where workers can innovate, transforming social challenges into long-term profitable strategies in tandem with conventional commercial endeavors (Dionisio & de Vargas, 2022). After that, it develops into partnerships that enhance the current frameworks by providing a distinct set of abilities, resources, and knowledge that enable businesses to create and execute social innovations and further create novel and inventive procedures that ultimately lead to quantifiable outcomes that are advantageous to both enterprises and society, more in line with the primary business objective (Mirvis & Googins, 2017).

Herrera (2015) observes that CSI requires more collaboration than typical corporate social responsibility, both within a corporation and with external partners. To be classified as CSI, an innovation must (1) address a social problem; (2) generate shared values; (3) build capacity for change; (4) form cross-sectoral partnerships; and (5) target system change (van der Have & Rubalcaba, 2016; Edwards-Schachter & Wallace, 2017; Mulgan, 2019); and (6) capture competitive advantage—to achieve business goals (Saka-Helmhout et al., 2024). According to this perspective of CSI, social innovation is transformative—an instrumental tool for finding business opportunities and co-creating market-based solutions as part of a company strategy (Mirvis et al., 2016; Tabares, 2020).

B. Community Development

Hale et al. (2023) defined community development broadly as the long-term improvement in the quality of interactions between people and places. Collective agency, or a group's ability to tackle common problems jointly, is central to this concept (Flora et al., 2016). As a result, community development is broader than economic development and focuses on what residents do to improve the entire quality of life in a given area (Hale et al., 2023). Notably, Hale et al. (2023) concentrated on development and related activities within place-based communities. They also opted to include terminology like "cultural resources" and "cultural assets" to account for discipline differences in how it is implemented. The process of increasing the strength and effectiveness of communities, improving people's quality of life, and allowing people to participate in decision-making to achieve greater long-term control over their lives is defined in the community development kit jointly issued by ICMM and the World Bank (International Council on Mining and Metals, 2005).

Scholars have given their ideas on how to better support local community development and improve corporate-community relationships through CD programs. Kemp and Owen (2013) believe that mining enterprises should prioritize activities linked to CD programs in enterprise organizations and accept them as one of their core businesses, allowing CD programs to be carried out more efficiently. Many researchers agree with this viewpoint (including Harvey, whose perspective on strategy differs from Kemp and Owen's) (Harvey, 2017). Scholars have investigated some of the important factors that influence CD programs as a result. The most commonly underlined component is participatory development. To promote participatory development, communications between businesses and communities, as well as between businesses, individuals, families, and groups, should be prioritized, according to Kemp (2009). Ballard and Banks (2003) emphasize the significance of multiple-party participation (such as NGOs and the government) in the process of CD programs. Bebbington et al. (2008) note that community participation should be valued in stages including program design, management, and the following evaluation.

Even though they focus on diverse aspects of participatory development, there is general agreement that participatory development is an important strategy for ensuring human rights, fairness, and community decision-making authority (Kemp, 2009). Trust between enterprises and local communities is another important factor that influences CD programs that many scholars pay close attention to (Bowen et al., 2010); ICCM points out that if there is a lack of trust among stakeholders, even the best program will fail. Banks et al. (2016) emphasize the significance of trust and mistrust issues between businesses and local communities in CD research. Additionally, studies are conducted to explore the classification, framework, implementation timing, and imbalanced rights issues in CD programs (Dhliwayo, 2013; Kemp, 2009). Eweje (2006) discusses the importance of trust in CD programs and believes that trust is crucial in realizing the desires of the local community and is the foundation for success.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research methodology adopts a comprehensive approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data. Data was gathered through surveys, questionnaires, and in-depth interviews with 15 LENTERA Sukamoro program participants, PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit, and local government heads and officials. The survey was conducted to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the community development program implemented by PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit in Sukamoro Village. In-depth interviews, on the other hand, were done to investigate the impact or changes experienced by participants after

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the community development program was implemented, as well as to assess the program's efficacy in resolving local concerns. Researchers can gain a full understanding of the community development program implemented by the PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit in Sukamoro Village by combining many of these methods.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Sukamoro Village Issues

Sukamoro Village is a sub-district of Talang Kelapa District, Banyuasin Regency, South Sumatra. According to 2019 IDM value data, Talang Kelapa District is classified as a developing village, with an index value of 0.6598. Given these circumstances, the PTBA Kertapati Pier Unit is interested in making Sukamoro Village one of the community development zones. The results of Sukamoro Village's social mapping validated this urgency. The results of social mapping conducted by PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit demonstrate the potential for community growth, which is accompanied by complex difficulties. The outcomes of this social mapping are shown in the table below:

Table 1. Identification of Problems in Sukamoro Village

Aspect	Issue
Social	<p>Unemployment The majority of Sukamoro Village residents, 4,400 in total, have a high school education, accounting for 28.04% of the entire population. This demonstrates that the residents of Sukamoro Village are well aware of the importance of education. However, this creates another issue, namely unemployment due to the large number of people of working age, which is not offset by adequate employment prospects. This is also influenced by the limited number of jobs that accept high school graduates. In addition, many housewives do not have work. Housewives are the most vulnerable to access and assets because they lack the necessary skills and cash to start a home company.</p>
	<p>Low Community Skills and Competency As previously stated, the majority of people in Sukamoro Village receive their highest level of education in high school. Education that only reaches the high school level can have an impact on the Sukamoro people's skills and competencies. The majority of people, particularly housewives, lack specialized skills and competencies that can be used to get better-paying jobs. Housewives in the Sukamoro Subdistrict lack specialized skills and productive activities that could create additional revenue to help fulfill household necessities.</p>
Economy	<p>Livelihood The majority of citizens work as vegetable farmers, with approximately 37% being farmers and farm laborers. Aside from farming, many people work as unskilled laborers, such as woodworkers, construction workers, and stone workers. Working as unskilled workers is a source of income for over 22% of Sukamoro Village residents. Aside from farming and unskilled labor, Sukamoro Village people also work as traders, civil servants, private employees, TNI, and police officers. Aside from that, many people do not have occupations, with housewives accounting for the vast majority of them. In Sukamoro Village, up to 15% of housewives are unemployed and solely responsible for home chores.</p>
	<p>Poverty The amount of revenue earned is affected by the livelihood of the people of Sukamoro Village, the majority of whom work as vegetable growers and unskilled laborers. As is well known, working as a vegetable farmer or unskilled laborer is a job with an unstable income. Farmers do not have a consistent income since they are extremely exposed to climate change and calamities, which cause crop yields to be uncertain and even result in crop failure. This can lead to economic difficulties. Aside from that, unskilled laborers have no job security and are highly dependent on whether or not there are projects to work on. This creates uncertainty in acceptable income, reducing one's ability to meet basic demands. Aside from that, the bulk of the community's wives, who work as vegetable farmers and unskilled laborers, do not have employment and are unable to support the family financially.</p>
Environment	<p>Inefficient Utilization of Natural Resources Sukamoro Village features springs with high mineral concentrations. However, local communities have not made optimal use of these natural riches. Many multinational enterprises use springs in Sukamoro Village to produce bottled drinking water.</p>
	<p>Existence of Unproductive Land Sukamoro Village has a large number of unproductive acres. This unproductive land is caused by the activities of mining red soil for brickmaking. Excavating this red soil produces several holes.</p>

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Aspect	Issue
	This excavated area turns into unproductive land.

Source: Social Mapping Document, 2020

B. Community Development Program "LENTERA Sukamoro"

PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit (PTBA Derti) is attempting to address complicated challenges in Sukamoro Village through empowerment recommendations that can be adopted. The corporation fulfills its efforts through a community empowerment initiative that engages all community groups, particularly housewives, to increase each family's income. This is also consistent with PTBA Derti's strategic plan for the 2020–2024 period, which states that community development issues include improving the quality of local human resources, developing community economic enterprises, utilizing natural resources for social purposes, and strengthening community institutions. These topics encompass Sukamoro Village's community development. This program was then carried out using a livestock agriculture business development paradigm in the LENTERA Sukamoro program. This program was chosen with urgency to improve the well-being of the inhabitants of Sukamoro Village quickly and without the need for special skills, so that all community groups, particularly housewives, could implement it. This program also aims to meet the demands of the Sukamoro Village community following the company's strategic plan for 2020–2024. The activities that have been carried out include:

Table 2. Activities of the Community Development Program "LENTERA Sukamoro"

Year	Activity	Activity Description
2020	Building a Catfish Tarpaulin Pond	PTBA Derti assists the community by providing fish tarpaulin ponds for catfish cultivation. This help is provided to one of Sukamoro Village's most disadvantaged groups, housewives, who do not engage in productive activities and lack specialized skills.
	Support for Catfish Seeds	PTBA Derti supplies catfish seeds to the community that manages Rule Athallah.
	Establishment of a Fishery Products Processing Group (POKLAHSAR)	PTBA Derti helped establish POKLAHSAR and legalize the Athallah Rule.
2021	Increasing the Quantity and Quality of Catfish Ponds	PTBA Derti assisted by increasing the number of catfish ponds and converting tarpaulin pools to concrete ponds. The pool was built on the location of a former red soil excavation pit that now serves as unproductive land.
	Help with Pool Pump	PTBA Derti assisted Rule Athallah by providing a pond pump to aid in the catfish cultivation process. Pool pump help is available to boost oxygen levels and make the water cleaner and clearer.
	Support with Transport Boxes	PTBA Derti provided Rule Athallah with transportation boxes to aid with the delivery of catfish goods.
2022	Development of Processed Catfish Products	PTBA Derti trains all Rule Athallah members in catfish processing. This is done to enhance the variety of product types available for sale while also improving Rule Athallah members' talents.
	Packaging Machine Assistance	PTBA Derti provides support in the form of packaging machinery in order to improve the efficiency and efficacy of the catfish product manufacturing process.
2023	Development of Processed Catfish Leftover Products	PTBA Derti trains all Rule Athallah members in the processing of catfish waste products. This is done to enhance the number of product varieties available for sale while also improving the abilities of Rule Athallah members.
	Transforming a Fish Pond Into a Reflection Pond	PTBA Derti transformed one catfish pond into a reflection pond.
	Solar Cell Installation	PTBA Derti gave aid by building four solar cell lighting stations around Rule Athallah's catfish pond.
	Catfish Cultivation in Karanganyar	PTBA Derti reproduced the community development program in the Karanganyar sub-district, offering catfish farming and processing training.

Source: Social Return on Investment (SROI) Document, 2023

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The LENTERA Sukamoro program's activities are divided into many forms of innovation. More information can be found in the following table:

Table 3. Program Innovation Classification

No.	Program/Product/Activity	Type of Innovation	Justification
1	LENERA Sukamoro Program	Radical Innovation	This program empowers vulnerable populations in Sukamoro Village, including housewives who are unemployed or do not have a job, to develop new business procedures and apply solar cell technology for catfish pond facilities.
2	MSME Rumah Lele Athallah	Sustaining Innovation	MSME Rumah Lele Athallah serves as a long-term sustainability mechanism for the LENTERA Sukamoro Program. This MSME is a platform for women to manage catfish production, processing, and marketing.

Source: Social Innovation Document, 2023

The LENTERA Sukamoro Program, as a form of PT. Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit, has succeeded in supporting the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which are as follows: Goal 1: No Poverty; Goal 2: Zero Hunger; Goal 5: Gender Equality; Goal 7: Affordable and Clean Energy; Goal 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth; Goal 12: Responsible Consumption and Production; and Goal 13: Climate Action. The sustainability compass demonstrates sustainability in the following four aspects:

Table 4. Sustainability Compass

Sustainability Aspect	Program Contribution	SDGs Goal
Nature	Using EBT solar cells to manage catfish ponds reduces energy consumption by 12.61 GJ per year. Turning leftover catfish bones into edible goods 0.012 tons of non-B3 rubber conveyor belt trash are used annually for v-belt cracker cutters.	Goal 7: Affordable and Clean Energy Goal 12: Responsible Consumption and Production Goal 13: Climate Action
Economy	One MSME business unit is established and nurtured. MSME Rule Athalla has worked with seven organizations and agencies. Rumah Lele Athallah's MSME turnover averages IDR 50,000,000 per month.	Goal 1: No Poverty Goal 2: Zero Hunger Goal 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth
Wellbeing	11 women and housewives are empowered. 10 men were employed. 100 beneficiaries become prosperous.	Goal 5: Gender Equality
Social	100 persons benefited from the LENTERA Sukamoro initiative, which resolved 5.95% of the impoverished in Sukamoro Village.	Goal 1: No Poverty Goal 2: Zero Hunger Goal 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

Source: Social Innovation Document, 2023

C. Most Significant Change Story

Enhancement of skills

Aside from caring for the household, the majority of housewives in Sukamoro Village lack specific skills or other profitable hobbies. Housewives receive various types of training through the Lentera Sukamoro Program, including catfish cultivation training with assistance from the Fisheries Service, catfish processing training, and digital marketing training provided directly by PTBA Derti employees, allowing them to market the products they produce. The different trainings provided have improved the abilities and capabilities of Athallah Rule housewives in fish cultivation, fishery product processing, business management, and marketing.

Figure 1. The Process of Producing Processed Catfish

Increased revenue

Housewives can be empowered as Rule Athallah members through PTBA Derti's Lentera Sukamoro Program to cultivate and process catfish into various high-value items. Rule Athallah has produced a variety of processed catfish products, including Ready-to-Fry Catfish (Lesgo), Smoked Catfish (Sale), Bekasam, Sambal Lingkung, Shredded Lele, Lele Bone Crackers, and Lele Skin Crackers. These numerous types of output are then packaged in an appealing manner and widely advertised. Sales of processed catfish products have resulted in an increased income of around IDR 3,400,000 for all Rule Athallah members, the majority of whom are housewives. Housewives can earn money through this activity to help satisfy their family's necessities. Housewives who are members of Rule Athallah earn money not only from selling processed catfish goods but also by selling tickets for reflection pool excursions.

Figure 2. Processed Catfish Products

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Figure 3. Reflection Pool

Access to Sustainable Energy

Rule Athallah began by using illumination from the PLN electricity installed in the fish pond. Rule Athallah has had solar cell lights placed at four spots around the catfish pond as part of PTBA Derti's Lentera Sukamoro Program. Installing solar cell lights to light catfish ponds significantly reduces Rule Athallah's operating costs.

Figure 4. Solar Cell Instalation

V. CONCLUSIONS

The LENTERA Sukamoro program was developed by PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit as a form of corporate social responsibility and in response to different community issues in the company's operations locations. The primary goal of this initiative is to promote the well-being of the community in Sukamoro Village, which is plagued by poor communal income, unproductive housewives, and limited skills. The LENTERA Sukamoro program is carried out through various activities, such as building tarpaulin pools, building reflection pools, catfish cultivation training, catfish processing training, using solar cells to light pools, training in making NPWP and business permits, training for business partners to upgrade, fish seed assistance for catfish, the formation of a fishery product processing group (POKLAHSAR), assistance with fish pond pumps, and packaging and branding training.

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This initiative generates benefits that considerably exceed the costs incurred. The success of the Lentera Sukamoro Program can be demonstrated by strengthening community capacity, leveraging existing assets and resources, addressing numerous community needs and challenges, and improving the community's quality of life. This program has successfully increased community capacity for catfish cultivation, processing, and commercialization. The training also improved the community's ability to overcome the issue of low income.

This program also improves the Sukamoro Village community's human resource management by involving unproductive housewives in Rumah Lele Athallah (Rule Athallah) activities. Overall, the LENTERA Sukamoro program has proven to be a successful example of how community empowerment projects may address environmental health issues and increase community welfare while developing a sustainable economic model. Aside from that, the considerable benefits and changes experienced by the people of Sukamoro Village cannot be separated from the involvement of PT Bukit Asam Dermaga Kertapati Unit (PTBA Derti), which has established programs and activities to meet the needs and characteristics of the Sukamoro Village community.

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